

Data Management Plan

PLASMASOLUTION

A Data Management Plan created using DMPOnline

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PROJECT ABSTRACT:

This action will implement the new Plasma-Enhanced Chemical Solution Deposition (PECSD) technique for coating of wood and wood-based substrates. This technique synergistically employs plasma-chemistry in the gas phase and polymer chemistry in the liquid formulation, thus combining all benefits of conventional surface coatings and plasma-based deposition technologies. The implementation is divided into three main objectives: Objective I: Building the integrated device, Objective II: Optimization of the deposition parameters, and Objective III: Demonstrating the technique's capability and priming the industrial implementation.

These objectives will lead to the generation of data:

- (I) on the construction, setup, and ongoing improvements of the device,
- (II) on the experimental protocols for film deposition and the properties of the resulting coatings, and
- (III) on the effectiveness of the demonstrated applications towards commercialization.

Various kinds and forms of data will be generated throughout the project. No previous works on this specific kind of approach are known from the literature, hence no reuse of existing data is foreseen.

1. DATA SUMMARY

PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION

The data is collected to validate the novel approach and demonstrate the new coating technology. The construction details, protocols, process parameters, and analytical measurements on the produced coatings all aim to fulfil the three objectives.

The raw data on plasma-treated and plasma-coated wood substrates might further be helpful for readers of our scientific articles that are to be published, allowing them to verify our findings. Thus, publishing all data allows achieving a more complete transparency and reproducibility. Furthermore, the data may help to form a more complete view on the effects of different plasma treatments on wood surfaces, and thus might enable to generate a general model covering all different plasma treatments.

RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE

The three main objectives of the action are: (I) Building an integrated device, (II) optimizing the parameters of PMMA deposition for exterior use, thereby further improving the understanding of the processes, and (III) demonstrating the technique's capability and priming the industrial implementation. The created data will therefore include:

- (I) Construction details and computer-aided design (CAD) assisted drawings,**
- (II) Coating deposition protocols, plasma diagnostic data, and data for the characterisation of the deposited coatings, as well as**
- (III) Aging, weathering and adhesion tests of the coatings, amongst other measurements, that indicate the industrial usability.**

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However, variables and types of the data required to fulfil these three objectives are too complex to be stated in one paragraph. These will be explored in more detail later within this plan.

TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA GENERATED/COLLECTED

(I) Construction details, CAD drawings, simulations:

- CAD drawings: SolidWorks; .sldprt, .sldasm, .slddrw / .pdf, .jpg
- Simulations: COMSOL Multiphysics; .mph / .pdf, .jpg
- EDA constructions: KiCad; .pro, .sch, .kicad_pcb, .net, .gbr / .pdf

(II) Coating deposition protocols, plasma diagnostic data, and data for the characterisation of the deposited coatings:

- Protocols: Word; .docx / .txt
- Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES) spectra: .xls / .pdf
- Tensiometer: KRÜSS Laboratory Desktop; .xls / .mdb
- Goniometer: Attension; .xls / .bmp, .png, .jpg
- Fourier-Transform InfraRed (FTIR) Spectrometer: Spectrum; .xls, .txt / .bmp, .png, .jpg, .gif, .tif
- Secondary Electron Microscope (SEM): xTmicroscope server; .tif
- Zwick Z100: Testxpert II; .xls files

(III) Aging, weathering and cross-cut tests of the coatings, amongst other measurements, that indicate the industrial usability:

- Images (Photographs); .jpg, .bmp
- Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy Olympus Lext: .poir, .rep / .jpg, .pdf

RE-USE OF EXISTING DATA

The project pursues a new approach and constructs novel technology in doing so. Therefore, no data exists than can directly be re-used. The construction and design are, however, based upon basic principles and findings from the past. All published findings and data will be linked to those, thus allowing to position the created data within the existing context.

ORIGIN OF THE DATA

All data is either created on the computer or recorded from original measurements and experiments. These relate to the three objectives as follows:

(I) Construction details, CAD drawings, simulations:

- CAD drawings: proprietary files (SolidWorks) as well as images and PDF
- Simulations: proprietary files (COMSOL Multiphysics) as well as images and PDF
- KiCad: open file formats (KiCad) as well as PDF and Gerber

(II) Coating deposition protocols, plasma diagnostic data, and data for the characterisation of the deposited coatings:

- Protocols: original notes
- OES spectra: original measurements
- Tensiometer: original measurements
- Goniometer: original measurements
- FTIR Spectrometer: original measurements
- SEM microscope: original measurements
- Zwick Z100: Testxpert II: original measurements

(III) Aging, weathering and cross-cut tests of the coatings, amongst other measurements, that indicate the industrial usability:

- Image from photo camera
- Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy: proprietary file formats (Olympus) as well as PDF and JPG

EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

(I) Construction details, CAD drawings, simulations:

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- CAD drawings:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
 - Simulations:
 - proprietary files few 100 MB, PDF files few MB
 - a total of up to 2 GB is expected
 - EDA constructions:
 - proprietary files few 100 kB, PDF files few MB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
- (II) Coating deposition protocols, plasma diagnostic data, and data for the characterisation of the deposited coatings:**
- Protocols:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 10 MB is expected
 - OES spectra:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
 - Tensiometer:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
 - Goniometer:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
 - FTIR Spectrometer:
 - each file will amount to few 10 kB
 - a total of up to 500 MB is expected
 - SEM microscope:
 - each file will amount to few MB
 - a total of up to 1 GB is expected
 - Zwick Z100: Testxpert II:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
- (III) Aging, weathering and cross-cut tests of the coatings, amongst other measurements, that indicate the industrial usability:**
- Photo camera:
 - each file will amount to few 100 kB
 - a total of up to 100 MB is expected
 - CLSM:
 - proprietary files typically 20 MB per measurement, PDF & JPG files few MB
 - a total of up to 100 GB is expected

In summary, a total of max. 105 GB is expected. The existing facilities for data storage at the University of Ljubljana allows to handle and store this data without extra costs.

DATA UTILITY: TO WHOM WILL IT BE USEFUL

- (I) Construction details and CAD drawings:**
- CAD drawings: academia and industry for reproduction, utilization for different applications, and to raise the quality of their final products for the end user.
 - Simulations: academia and industry for adaption for further applications
- (II) Coating deposition protocols, plasma diagnostic data, and data for the characterisation of the deposited coatings:**
- Protocols: academia and industry for adaption and reproduction
 - OES, Tensiometer, Goniometer, FTIR, SEM, and Zwick: academia for reproduction and verification
 - KiCad constructions: academia and industry as well as DIY communities and tech enthusiasts

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(III) Aging, weathering and cross-cut tests of the coatings, i.a.: academia for reproduction and verification

2.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA [FAIR DATA]

DISCOVERABILITY OF DATA AND METADATA PROVISION

All data will be uploaded together with the relating metadata, including project context and labbook entries. These collections will be linked to scientific articles, conference proceedings, reports, and other sources to be published.

IDENTIFIABILITY OF DATA AND STANDARD MECHANISM, USE OF PERSISTENT AND UNIQUE IDENTIFIERS

We will make use of persistent and unique Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) via the data storage facility. A description of available data collections will also be added to the PIs website.

NAMING CONVENTIONS

We ascertain that the data will be easily recognized and correlated to experiments via the following naming conventions:

- Raw data: YYYYMMDD_[experiment]_[technique]_XXX.*
- Processed results: YYYYMMDD_[experiment]_[technique]_XXX_analysis_ZZZ.*

Herein, symbols represent the following:

YYYYMMDD inverted date of the day the experiment was conducted
[experiment] short title for the experimental series
[technique] unique denominator for each technique, such as CLSM, SEM
XXX running number for individual measurements
ZZZ running number for versioning during separate processes of analysis

Same naming formats will be used for other data, such as CAD and COMSOL files.

APPROACH TOWARDS SEARCH KEYWORD

Documentation and notes are centrally stored in text or markdown formats together with the original (raw) data. Findability is ascertained by the naming convention. No additional approach towards search keywords is foreseen to be required, as typical keywords are given by the techniques' unique names.

APPROACH FOR CLEAR VERSIONING

Versioning of both, raw data from repeated experiments as well as processed data during analysis, is included in the naming convention via separate running numbers.

STANDARDS FOR METADATA CREATION

No field-specific recommendations are known to the PI at the point of the DMP creation. As metadata, we will thus provide:

- Publication date,
- Title,
- Authors including contact information,
- Description,
- Version,
- Language,
- Keywords,
- Grant acknowledgement, and
- References to all publications referring to the dataset.

Further, we will include complete lab notebook excerpts, as well as protocols for measurements and analysis within the dataset.

This is fully in line with the repository's policy. Further, the repository stores all metadata in JSON-format according to a defined JSON schema. Metadata is exported in several standard formats such as MARXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema in accordance with the OpenAIRE Guidelines.

